

MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL CRISIS SITUATIONS IN EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract:

The nowadays educational organizations have to keep up with the changes in the society and so does the school manager. We will take a look on how the educational organizations function, what are the main qualities of a school manager and we will dive into the topic of how to solve and manage the educational crisis situations. My study is focusing on how to become a successful and efficient school manager and on the methods that should be applied in order to maintain efficient work, deliverance of education, a healthy work environment for the school staff and in order to manage and overcome the educational crisis situations.

Keywords: school management, educational organizations, managing qualities, effective teaching, educational crisis situations.

The concept of management is becoming more and more common nowadays, as it is a real topical idea that is still being debated and rediscovered both by researchers and specialists and by people who take on this role in organisations or companies.

Although it is often confused with leadership, management is distinguished by its own characteristics, which we will observe throughout the paper, where we will explore and gain an overview of two concepts, at first glance identical, but so different in their depth.

Situations of educational crisis are a phenomenon that is often unavoidable. All organisations face crisis situations, with schools being the most concerned due to the large influx of people differing in many aspects and the many factors we are about to identify.

The complexity of educational crisis situations puts us in the position of researching, discovering, learning and applying new methods to manage them. The most important thing is to gain new knowledge and manage the situation as quickly and effectively as possible.

Appropriate and effective management of educational crisis situations can have several beneficial effects such as developing better communication and changing perspective as well as situation. Behaviours can be shaped in a positive and harmonious way.

Organisations are a vital aspect of human life. The coordination of human life and its activities is due to organisations. Because of lack of organisation in every area of life, there will be dispersion and uncertainty. Organisation itself is a vast phenomenon and applies to every aspect of life. From an educational point of view, we can describe organisations as a broad institution that is responsible for coordinating and directing training and information activities that lead to the satisfaction of the needs of learners.

Effective management requires organisation. It acts as a preface to any activity and plays an important role. It helps the teacher to use his/her skills and consistency in different parts of the school. It is a vital fact that the basic purpose of organization is organization and distribution as personnel, distribution of sources and resources. In short, the basic function of the organization is to do useful work and function as a whole.

The chosen theme is topical and high-impact. Managing educational crisis situations in schools will be approached from the perspective of the manager of the educational organisation, the head teacher. This approach is much broader and more complex than from the perspective of the teacher, who is (in most cases) only confronted with educational crisis situations in his/her classroom.

We have paid particular attention to the perspective of the institution manager because he/she coordinates and directs educational crisis situations at the level of the institution, which constantly forces him/her to discover new methods and strategies to manage conflicts and educational crisis situations, to communicate effectively and assertively, to mould him/herself to the given situations and to create a pleasant and favourable educational environment for both the beneficiaries and the human resource in his/her unit.

I. Educational crisis situations in school organisations

Situations of educational crisis can be defined as moments or periods of time when the education system is experiencing significant

difficulties that affect its ability to provide quality education and to achieve its objectives and goals. These difficulties may be of a diverse nature, such as financial problems, political or social changes, natural disasters or other situations affecting the educational environment. In general, educational crises are characterised by a deterioration in the quality of education, reduced access to education and/or the emergence of inequalities in the education system. These situations can have long-term negative effects on individual and collective education and development.

So we understand the impact of the educational crisis on educational organisations and institutions through the lens of the change it brings about. There are also many different types of educational crisis and causes.

There are several causes of educational crisis, and these can vary by country and region. In the following, we explore the causes and factors of educational crises, classifying them according to several criteria:

a) Lack of funding - many countries under-invest in education, which can lead to a lack of resources and low quality of education.

b) Inadequate education system - the education system may be outdated and unable to meet the needs and expectations of students and society at large. There may also be problems with the quality of teachers, the curriculum and teaching methods.

c) Social and economic problems - economic problems, such as poverty and social inequality, can affect access to education and student performance. Discrimination and social inequality can also lead to a lack of access to education for certain groups of pupils.

d) Outdated technology - rapid technological change can lead to inadequate education systems and teaching methods. Lack of access to technology and resources can also limit student performance.

e) Lack of political attention - education can be a low priority in public policy, which can lead to underfunding and lack of interest from government and society at large.

Unlike classroom crises, crises in school organisations can be much more far-reaching and naturally have a much greater impact. These 'problems' are for the school manager, the head teacher, to manage quickly and effectively.

As specialist Romița Iucu has stated, the types of educational crisis are as follows:

a) Depending on the degree of development:

- o Instantaneous - this is triggered in an unexpected way and can become a real obstacle if not managed in time.

- o Intermittent - disappears following intervention measures but reappears after a certain period of time

b) by degree of relevance:

- o Critical - can lead to the breakdown of the organisation in which they appeared

- o Major - have significant effects but do not prevent recovery

c) by the number of subjects involved

- o Individual

- o Group

- o Collective, global

Throughout the work we have observed the impact of effective and assertive communication, or lack thereof, in managing educational crisis situations. Given this, I believe it is necessary to explore in detail what is meant by the term effective and assertive communication, its importance and how it should be used.

Effective and assertive communication refers to the ability to convey clear and concise messages without being aggressive or passive in tone. It involves communicating with clarity, but also with respect for the other person and the ability to express one's own needs and opinions in an appropriate way. Assertiveness is closely linked to empathy.

Active listening is an important component of effective and assertive communication. We should try to be present when we are talking to someone and try to understand their point of view before expressing our opinion. We also need to stay focused on the facts and avoid making statements that are based on feelings or assumptions. This will help reduce tension and make it easier for the other person to understand the message.

Tone of voice can have a strong impact on how the message is perceived. It is necessary to use a clear and calm tone without being

aggressive or passive. Effective and assertive communication refers to the ability to communicate clearly and persuasively without being aggressive or defensive in expression. It involves the ability to express your point of view openly and honestly without infringing on the rights and feelings of others.

Educational crisis situations can be caused by various events, it is important to develop crisis management plans to deal with these situations and minimise their impact on the learning process. Managing an educational crisis situation requires adequate planning and preparation, open and transparent communication, providing emotional support and ensuring the safety of all involved.

Having explored what educational crisis situations are, their characteristics and types, both at the classroom level and at the level of the educational organization, it is time to answer the question: how do we solve educational crisis from a school manager's position?

Retreat combines poor concern for both the success of the organization and relationships with subordinates.

The manager who uses this strategy sees conflict as hopelessly unresolvable, tries to avoid the frustration and stress that inevitably accompany it, withdraws from the conflict, or pretends it doesn't exist.

One of the consequences of ignoring the conflict is to block communication from both the bottom up and the top down, which makes things even worse. This approach to conflict can be advantageous, however, if the conflict situation does not matter.

Appeasement is characterised by the manager trying to deal with the conflict by pleasing everyone. It overestimates the value of maintaining relationships with subordinates and underestimates the importance of achieving objectives.

Forcing is an approach to conflict used by the manager who tries to achieve productivity goals at all costs, without considering the opinion or agreement of others, their needs and feelings. He will resort to coercive actions, using various financial, intellectual, ethical means, based on the power and authority granted by the position.

Through emotional implications, the language used generates negative feelings, dissatisfaction, frustration, humiliation. Force may resolve the dispute for the moment, but in the long term even more serious conflicts may arise.

Compromise lies somewhere between the 'force' and 'appeasement' approach and consists of resolving conflict issues through mutual concessions, with both sides achieving some satisfaction. It is often used in negotiations.

I also want to add an essential guide for negotiators in a conflict:

- Develop a clear set of objectives for each step of the negotiation and clarify the context in which these objectives were adopted.

- Don't be nervous.

- When you're not sure, err on the side of caution.

- Be well prepared with sufficient, clear and relevant arguments to support your objectives.

- Be flexible in the position you take and start from the premise that negotiation, by its very nature, involves some waivers and compromises.

- Try to understand the other side's reasoning. If you don't make progress, leave it to someone else and come back when the impasse has been broken. Use the moment to reach an understanding, relating to one of the issues under discussion.

- Follow up on any reactions from the other party.

- Control your emotions

- "Build" a reputation as an honest but firm man.

- Listen carefully to your partner's position,

- Carefully "weigh" each step forward in the negotiation and assess the impact of these agreements on the future course of negotiations.

- Assess the impact of each waiver on the objectives with which you started the negotiations.

- Consider the impact of the present negotiations on the period ahead

In conclusion, an effective manager is essential in resolving conflicts and maintaining a positive and productive working environment in an organisation.

II. Managerial strategies for solving educational crises and their role

Management refers to the process of planning, organising, coordinating and controlling an organisation's resources to achieve its objectives. It includes making decisions, managing people and other resources, and developing and implementing strategies.

School management strategy refers to the approach to planning, organising and controlling educational activities and resources to

achieve the school's objectives in an efficient and effective way. This strategy involves defining clear objectives and action plans to achieve these objectives, as well as managing and optimising the school's resources, such as human, financial, technological and material resources.

The main responsibilities of a school principal include:

- Planning and organising educational programmes and school activities;
- Human resource management, including recruitment and evaluation of teachers and support staff;
- Administering the school budget and managing financial resources;
- Creating and maintaining a safe and healthy environment for pupils and school staff;
- Communicating with parents and the local community;
- Developing relationships with other schools and educational institutions;
- Monitoring and evaluating school and student performance.

We can see how the unit director sets the tone for the unit's activities, coordinating them closely, with great responsibility and precision, the impact being truly significant. Everyone working in the unit expects the manager to coordinate, to develop human resources, to rethink the organisation and the school both as an entity and as a concept, and last but not least, to make the most of relations with teaching, non-teaching and auxiliary staff, pupils and teachers.

Management strategy in schools can also be influenced by the socio-economic, political and cultural context in which the school operates. Managers need to consider these factors and develop strategies that respond to their needs and requirements.

In the literature, the best-known classification of leadership styles is that which distinguishes between autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire models (Kurt Lewin - founder of social psychology).

The leader who practices an autocratic style:

- Sets the policies, the way of working and the tasks;
- is not necessarily hostile but makes decisions without consulting others.

This style leads to a high level of resistance and dissatisfaction from subordinates. The style is best used in crisis situations and when the situation is urgent.

The leader who practices a democratic style:

- Sets the policies of the organisation in a collective process;
- is interested in subordinates' ideas and perspectives on objectives and activities.

The style is valued by employees, ensures good working relationships and effectiveness of the work. Because consultation takes time, it is not recommended for urgent tasks.

The laissez-faire leader:

- Does not get involved in decision-making unless asked;
- gives employees complete freedom of decision and action;
- takes no interest in their work.

It is also necessary to talk about the steps to be taken in managing educational crisis situations:

1. Identification and knowledge of crisis situations (it is appropriate for the beginning of the analysis to particularize crisis situations at the level of the school, the group of students, interpersonal relationships, etc.).

2. The etiology of the crisis situation (need for in-depth knowledge of the situation but also of the causes). The role of the school manager is not to blame, to blame, to stigmatise individuals and actions, but to emphasise the idea of cooperation in resolving the crisis.

3. Decision-making: Since crisis situations require a high degree of operational efficiency, any minute lost in the early stages can turn into days of searching and effort later on. This is why crisis periods, which are atypical events, require not only promptness and speed from the teacher, but also options for resolution.

4. Intervention programme: even if the preliminary decision has been taken, as a type of much-needed immediate intervention, for the long-term perspectives the lines of evolution and alternatives for secondary decisions must be drawn.

5. In the implementation of measures, the common goal orientation, the elimination of hostilities and suspicions, and the positioning of all those involved as active participants in the process of solving the crisis, must be constant features of the actions of the teaching staff.

6. Control must accompany any action taken; its importance lies in the need to locate the phenomenon as accurately as possible and to avoid and prevent other effects of the crisis or even parallel micro-

analyses. The thoroughness of interventions, the degree of homogeneity and consistency are checked and optimised by means of monitoring.

7. The evaluation aims to measure and assess the final state of the group after the resolution process has been completed. An essential objective of the evaluation stage is to draw conclusions from the impact of the crisis and to engage all those involved in actions to understand and prevent future situations of this kind.

We also must talk about the concept of organisational behaviour which refers to the study of how people interact within organisations. It focuses on the behaviour of employees and how it influences the performance of the organisation. In general, organisational behaviour focuses on factors such as culture, communication, motivation, leaders and teams.

Management and organisational behaviour are closely linked and are essential to the success of organisations. By understanding how people behave in educational organizations and using effective management practices, educational organizations can increase productivity and satisfaction, improve relationships with participants in the instructional-educational act and process, and gain a beneficial advantage to the educational system.

A genuine conflict resolution programme has three components:

1. a set of principles designed to solve problems;
2. a structured process;
3. skills for creative cooperation between individuals and between groups.

A crucial topic to touch on throughout this paper is organizational psychology. In order to explore in depth, the work and even the effectiveness of a manager of an educational organisation we need to study and seek to understand how school organisations work.

It should be noted that educational organisations are somewhat different from other organisations/corporations we know. Educational institutions have a mission like any other institution and organisation, they have employees, beneficiaries, a dedicated space for work and even a manager who is in charge of managing them.

Organisational psychology can be used to understand how members of a school team work together, how to improve communication

between students and teachers, how to foster a culture of collaboration and continuous learning.

III. Final Conclusions

Throughout this paper we have explored in depth the key competencies of a manager of an educational organisation, the challenges they face, how they need to communicate both effectively and assertively, managerial strategies in the context of leadership and management, methods of managing educational crisis situations as well as what they are, their levels and how they manifest themselves but also the psychosociology behind educational organisations which helps the manager to understand their role and status, effective and assertive communication and how educational organisations work.

The paper was approached from the perspective of the manager of an educational organization who coordinates and manages educational crisis situations at the institutional level, uses managerial methods and strategies, communicates effectively and creates a harmonious and conducive educational environment for both learners and the human resource working within the educational organization.

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